

How can I integrate teaching features of connected speech to develop C1 student's listening decoding skills?

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Word count: 3298

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Verification pro forma

Verification pro forma for the unobserved teaching practice

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Lesson	Organisation	Class Identification	Time of class	Date of class	No. of Students	Signature of verifying teacher
1	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14 ³⁰ - 16 ⁰⁰	3.05.2019	1	[Signature]
2	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14 ³⁰ - 16 ⁰⁰	8.05.2019	1	[Signature]
3	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14:30-16:00	10.05.2019	1	[Signature]
4	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14:30-16:00	15.05.2019	1	[Signature]
5	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14 ³⁰ - 16 ⁰⁰	17.05.2019	1	[Signature]
6	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14 ³⁰ - 16 ⁰⁰	22.05.2019	1	[Signature]
7	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14:30-16:00	24.05.2019	1	[Signature]
8	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14:30-16:00	29.05.2019	1	[Signature]
9	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14:30-16:00	31.05.2019	1	[Signature]
10	"Smilies"	Speak. Adv.	14:30-16:00	5.05.2019	1	[Signature]
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Comment as necessary

Part 1. Background

1. Rationale

As a language teacher, I have met many people who successfully passed the well-recognized international exams but could not make sense of a casual conversation. My Chinese student Sherry is a perfect example of the above. After more than 30 years of learning English, she has achieved CERF C1 level but still finds it extremely difficult to understand fast English speech. It is highly problematic for Sherry, who regularly communicates with her native-speaking colleagues. She has admitted that the lack of comprehension affects her self-confidence.

Considering the importance of listening for communication, it is surprising that very few language schools offer listening courses, whereas various reading, writing and speaking programs are quite ubiquitous. I plan to compensate for this gap in my project as listening skill is essential for the overall communicative competence. Many students cannot even begin to participate in a conversation because of their lack of listening ability (Thorn: 2012); it often affects their social life and work integration, as happened to Sherry.

1.2 Conventional approach to teaching listening

As one of the core skills, listening is integrated into almost every ELT coursebook, but rarely in its authentic form. A massive gap between CSM (careful speech model) and SSM (spontaneous speech model) is almost never made explicit to the learners. ELT methodology has systematically avoided 'the painful fact that fast spontaneous speech is difficult for learners' (Cauldwell: 2002).

Over the past few decades, teaching listening was heavily dominated by the comprehensive approach. It claims comprehension to be the final aim of listening. In order to achieve it in the classroom, the input must be comprehensible, which is not always true in real life. Carefully articulated speech gives learners an illusion of understanding, breaking down as they leave the class. The comprehensive approach resembles testing comprehension and does little or nothing to teach it (Hancock, 2012). As a result, many learners achieve a high level of listening success in the classroom but find themselves ill-equipped for the outside world's demands (Field: 2008).

1.3 Focus of the project

In my project, I have adopted the idea of pronunciation for listening. Underhill puts it briefly - 'mouth teaches ear' (2004). Hancock argues there is no better way for a learner to become aware of something receptively than actually attempting to produce it (2012). Similarly, Cauldwell recommends using the patterns of SSM for both listening and pronunciation (2013). Field believes that speaking patterns shape our listening comprehension. He argues that when the brain gets an impulse from outside, it automatically refers to the mental trace existing there, matches two sound shapes, and detects the word (2008).

Connected speech 'consists of a flow of sounds which are modified by a system of simplifications through which phonemes are connected' (Underhill:2004, 58). Raising awareness about those 'simplifications' can enhance students' listening ability (Kelly: 2018). 'When learners become aware that a number of phonemes they might expect to hear are not actually produced, and when they discover that they can make these sounds disappear in their own speech, they begin to get an insight which helps them when they listen to rapid connected English' (Underhill: 2004, 62).

- **Objective 1**

To raise student's awareness about the components of connected speech. It is expected that she could quickly identify the features of connected speech in a text by the end of the project.

- **Objective 2**

To help the learner apply some of those principles in her reading and potentially speaking.

- **Goal**

Based on the achievement of both objectives, I hope my learner will become more effective in decoding small samples of spontaneous speech and will generally find authentic listening less inhibiting.

Part 2. The structure and the content of the lessons

2.1 Procedure and ethics

A total of ten 90-minute lessons were delivered to Sherry over three months. A combination of receptive and productive activities was used to deliver and practice the project content. The student agreed to participate in the project and spend all her paid lesson time on the project content. Sherry was aware that the lessons were filmed for research purposes. The video materials were never used publicly and were deleted soon after the project was over.

I used the episodes from a UK movie called 'Notting Hill' (1999) as the materials for noticing and decoding at home. After each lesson, I asked Sherry to watch a movie clip, write down the conversation she heard and highlight the instances of the phonemic transformations; then practice reading it, focusing on the highlights.

I have used the movie scenes because they set the context and link the assignments throughout the project. Also, as the samples of real communication, movie dialogues present a great value in terms of authenticity. Sherry loved the idea; she watched 'Notting Hill' long ago and was happy to see it again in chunks. The romantic story and the splendid acting boosted her enjoyment and helped maintain her motivation high.

The structure of the lessons 1-5:

1. Elicitation of a new rule

I provided a set of examples and encouraged Sherry to notice a typical phonological pattern shared by all of them.

2. Discovery activity

With my help, Sherry discovered the place and manner of articulation which helped her understand why the sounds shift in a particular way.

3. Noticing and controlled practice task

At the end of each lesson, Sherry highlighted the features of connected speech in a printed dialogue and read them aloud. It helped her remember which sounds transform in which way. Before Sherry developed her muscle memory, she had to notice and apply the rules consciously.

2.2 Reflections

Lessons 1-3 Assimilation

Assimilation is highly ubiquitous in English, but Sherry never heard about it. She was surprised that the particular combinations of sounds go through radical transformations without affecting intelligibility (Jenkins: 2012).

Lesson 1

By just exposure to the examples, Sherry struggled to guess the pattern. I explained how the articulation shifts in the flow of fast speech. As a result, the sounds at the boundaries of the words become more similar, as suggested by the name 'assimilation'.

- 1) /n/ + /p/, /b/, /w/, /m/ → /m/
 - Ten pairs
 - Green park
 - In Paris
 - On Wednesday

- Ten bottles

2) /t/ + /p/, /b/, /m/ → /p/

- Sit properly
- Hate potatoes
- Fat boy
- Cute baby
- That book

3) /d/ + /b/, /p/, /m/ → /b/

- Good boy
- Red ball
- Speed boat
- Sad mum
- Mad policy

The content was quite overwhelming to Sherry; she looked puzzled and kept repeating, 'It's difficult.' I asked her to read the examples a few times, focusing on what happens inside her mouth. I drew her attention to the physical side of assimilation. I ensured her once she gets used to it, she will find it easy and natural. My explanations helped her overcome her initial frustration.

Lesson 2

Sherry started to realize why she failed to understand the familiar words. 'It means the words I know I never hear, I hear something else, that's really tricky! Why? Why they didn't teach me?!' she said.

1) /s/ + /j/, /ʃ/, /t/ → /ʃ/

- Bless you
- This shirt
- Class teacher
- Makes you angry
- Glass table

2) /t/ + /j/ → /tʃ/

- Meet you
- Can't you
- Aren't you
- Got you
- Not usual

3) /d/+/j/ → /dʒ/

- Did you
- Would you
- Loud yawn
- Red yoyo
- Cold yogurt

In the end, Sherry said it was unbelievable that sounds changed so drastically. I replied that the good news was that those changes were predictable and learnable, not chaotic as she thought before. Sherry agreed that breaking connected speech into elements makes it look 'easier.'

Lesson 3

Sherry arrived at the lesson in a positive mood. 'Better, Kate, really better,' she replied to my question about her homework. By then, Sherry understood the principle of assimilation well; she quickly figured out the following patterns.

- 1) /t+/g/, /k/ → /k/
 - Credit card
 - Get cold
 - Do it quickly
 - Short cut
 - That cake

- 2) /d+/k/, /g/ → /g/
 - Bad girl
 - Good cook
 - Had guests
 - Hard copy
 - Red carpet

- 3) /z+/ʃ/ → /ʒ/
 - Cheese shop
 - Quiz show
 - Cruise ship
 - Lose shape
 - Chinese shark soup

- 4) /n+/k/, /g/ → /ŋ/
 - I've been going
 - Own car
 - Tin can
 - I mean green
 - Can go

Overall, Sherry found the phenomena of assimilation quite surprising, which made me think that the vast majority of learners are unaware of this transformation and unlikely to infer it without teacher's prompt.

It became evident that the original plan needed some adjustment. Ninety minutes were hardly enough for the home task, input, noticing, and production. No decoding, therefore, was included in the first part of the project.

Lessons 4-5 Elision

Elision presents a significant challenge for comprehension; seemingly simple omitting of one consonant could make the words sound differently.

Lesson 4

The amount of input was moderate, which allowed for more extended practice, including some free production. In the end, I asked Sherry to make her examples of elision, but it was not time efficient. Instead, drilling could be a more reasonable use of time.

- 1) /t/, /d/
 - Next day
 - Can't stand

- Let me go
- Don't know
- Must be

2) Consonants clusters

- sandwich
- handbag
- grandparents
- salt and pepper
- stand by

Sherry concluded, 'We need to be lazy; we do too much work (*pronouncing every sound*).' I agreed, 'otherwise, we would sound robotic.'

Lesson 5

This lesson focused on the particular instances of elision in grammar words. As Sherry became familiar with the format of work, our lessons started to flow more dynamically. It enabled me to include two micro-listening tasks.

1) /v/

- Waste of time
- Piece of cake
- Cup of tea
- The least of my worries
- 11th of November

1 **1.11** Listen to and read the phrases that go with these pictures. The phrases are written wrongly. Rewrite them correctly.

1 a cup a tea an a biscuit

4 a pine to milk an a loafer bread

2 one a two bags are ice

5 as coal does a block a vice

3 try a neat a bitter fruit

6 a piece a cake an a nice cream

2) /h/

- I saw him
- I told her
- I have a baby
- I'll ask him

2 1.62 All of these verb phrases contain forms of *be* and *have*. Listen to 12 fragments and number the phrases in the order you hear them.

- was going to leave were carrying was found
 were never seen has grown has never been
 has replaced might have been must have been
 must have got would have written would've been solved

Sherry noticed that elision erased the word boundaries; words merged and acquired a new phonetic outlook. I reminded her, 'Our ears hear what our brain expects to hear; our brain expectations are formed by how we speak. For example, if our brain knows that 'he is' can be pronounced only as /hi:ɪz/, it is unlikely that it could decode what /ɪəz/ means. So the more word forms we 'upload' to our brain, the better decoding we might hope for.' I find the time on explanation well worth spent as understanding is essential for analytical students like Sherry.

Lesson 6. The practice of assimilation and elision

Having done little decoding so far, I decided to have an intensive listening lesson. Sherry said that at home, she realized that elision was very common. She shared her discovery with me: 'He is sitting next to me' will be /ɪsɪtɪŋkɪsmɪ/. That's crazy!' The fact that Sherry was familiar with IPA meant I could incorporate transcriptions in my future lessons.

1 The underlined word in each sentence sounds like one of the words in the box. Listen and check.

EXAMPLE torch / talk

- talk / torch a I taught classes this morning. talk
 b You taught yourself French. torch

- 1 a The sun burnt my neck. _____
 b The sun came up over the mountains. _____

- 2 a I can't beat you at this game. _____
 b I can beat Carol at tennis. _____

- 3 a I can't get this coat clean. _____
 b Is this the coat you bought? _____

- 4 a They cheat quite a lot. _____
 b They cheat people out of their money. _____

2 2.53 Listen to and read these fragments. The words in bold are written as they sound. Correct them.

- 1 and this is **exackly**
- 2 **infeck** cancer cells
- 3 any bad side **effecks**
- 4 up on the north-**wess** coast
- 5 **perfeck** vision
- 6 the **easiess** thing to see
- 7 exchange of **giffs**
- 8 **rainforess**
- 9 the **satistics** of this
- 10 the thing is, is not about looking backwards, is about looking forwards

3 If a speaker doesn't pronounce a /t/ or /d/ at the end of the word, it sometimes sounds as if they're saying something else. What do you think these speakers were really saying?

- 1 Better luck necks time! Better luck next time!
- 2 Would you like a coal drink?
- 3 Who bill the pyramids?
- 4 I fell very tired last night.
- 5 I one to hole your hand.
- 6 I when to the doctor's yesterday.

4 Think of a computer which people speak into and it writes what they say. This computer wrote these sentences incorrectly. Listen. Guess from the context which word is wrong, circle it and write the correct word.

EXAMPLE (Watch) your name? What's

- 1 I hate going to museums and arc galleries.
- 2 Have you ever tribe Belgian beer?
- 3 I got ache questions correct out of ten.
- 4 She's a good player and can wing games against most people.
- 5 He copied out the text lime by line.
- 6 It was a bag question; nobody got the answer right.

5 2.55 Listen to and read these fragments. as they sound. Correct them.

- 1 the **goog** guys
- 2 and it **coob** be like almost harassing you or
- 3 the virus **kung** carry in a protein
- 4 **coob** be good at this
- 5 we **womp** more
- 6 you **shub** be polite
- 7 cruising **ing** company
- 8 I **cump** bear to watch it
- 9 **cum** be more than the sum of their parts

During decoding, Sherry referred to her notes; she lived through her 'a-ha' moment when everything she learnt suddenly worked together. Sherry found a 'listen and repeat' strategy advantageous. When she failed to understand the acoustic blur, she repeated exactly what she heard a few times; it helped her catch the right mental trace.

In the end, I gave Sherry a fun task; I asked her to guess who was Joanna and Anita and how they were related to our lesson. It took her a few minutes to guess the answer 'Do you want to?' and 'I need to.' For more fun and free listening activities, I recommended the following websites [Hancock McDonald ELT](#) and [Speech in Action – In touch with real speech](#).

Lessons 7-8 Vowel reduction

Lesson 7 /ə/ in grammar words

I introduced the notion of stress vs. unstress in the individual words first. Sherry noticed that unstressed syllables often contained a 'schwa' sound. Then I expanded the same idea to the level of utterance where the unstressed words often get reduced to a series of 'schwa-s.' Listeners perceive a combination of unstressed words in a sentence as acoustic blur (Cauldwell: 2013).

Keeping in mind that decoding grammar words present a significant challenge even for advanced learners (Field: 2008), I gave Sherry a list of the function words in their weak forms (Kelly:2018). Sherry was genuinely delighted; she said this is 'the most useful thing' and that I should have given it to her earlier. Next time teaching this course, I will consider introducing vowel reduction before assimilation and elision.

Grammatical category	Word	Full form	Weak form	Example of weak form
Verbs	am	æm	m	That's what I'm trying to say.
	are	ɑ:	ə	Where are you from?
	is	ɪz	əz/z/s	Where's he from?/Where is he from?
	was	wɒz	wəz	That's where he was born.
	were	wɜ:	wə	That's where my children were born.
	do	du:	də	Where do you live?
	does	dʌz	dəz	Where does he live?
	have	hæv	əv/v	He will have left by now./They've gone.
	has	hæz	həz/əz/z/s	The baby has swallowed a stone./He's gone.
	had	hæd	həd/əd/d	He had already gone./He'd already gone.
	can	kæn	kən	I'm not sure if I can lend it to you.
	could	kʊd	kəd	Well, what could I say?
	would	wʊd	wəd/əd	Well, what would you have done?
	should	ʃʊd	ʃəd/ʃd	Well, what should I have said?
Personal pronouns	you	ju:	jə	How do you do?
	your	jɔ:	jə	What does your boss think?
	he	hi:	hi/ɪ	Where does he work?
	him	hɪm	ɪm	I'll give it to him later.
	she	ʃi:	ʃɪ	She's leaving tomorrow.
	her	hɜ:	hə/ə	I'll give it to her later.
	us	ʌs	əs	They'll give it to us later.
	them	ðem	ðəm	I'll give it to them later.
Prepositions	to	tu:	tə	He's already gone to work.
	at	æt	ət	He's at work, I think.
	of	ɒv	əv	That's the last of the wine!
	for	fɔ:	fə	He's away for two weeks.
	from	fɹɒm	fɹəm	She comes from Scotland.
Conjunctions	and	ænd	ən/ənd	She's tall and fair.
	but	bʌt	bət	She's here, but Juan isn't.
	than	ðæn	ðən	She's older than you.
Articles	a	eɪ	ə	He's a doctor.
	an	æn	ən	She's an architect.
	the	ði:	ðə	She's the person I told you about.
Indefinite adjectives	any	eni:	əni:/ni:	Have we got any biscuits?
	some	sʌm	səm	There's some tea in the pot.
	such	sʌtʃ	sətʃ	It's not such a big deal, really.

Relying on the table above, we did the following tasks.

- 1 **1.60** In each of the sentences below, the part in bold has been misunderstood. Listen and decide what the speaker actually wanted to say, using words and phrases from the box.

is are was were have has ~~I was~~ have been there was

- hours** two years old I was two years old
- my **watches** broken
- the man, who **as** a doctor
- though as** only one left
- it must **of bin** terrible
- the place **as** changed a lot
- the birds **a** singing
- they must **of** gone
- I thought you **a** French

- 2 **1.61** Listen and complete these fragments of speech with a form of *be*: *is, are, was, were*.

- 1 which _____ in Washington state
- 2 because they _____ interested in what _____ going on
- 3 and this _____ exactly
- 4 Evelyn _____ my grandmother
- 5 I _____ two years old
- 6 for your colleagues who _____ in the field
- 7 things that _____ there at the time of the eruption
- 8 what's exciting _____ that we now
- 9 and we realized that it _____ actually working loose

Decoding turned out to be very difficult and time-consuming; Sherry was sighing and looked desperate. I played the fragments multiple times before Sherry could decode them. In the end, Sherry said, 'Well, now I understand how they speak so fast.'

Lesson 8 /ə/ in 'rushed' adverbs and filler words

I told Sherry that sometimes she might hear something completely incomprehensible in the middle of the sentence, like 'a chewing gum' (Hancock: 2014). I intended to acknowledge her that she could practically ignore some pieces of the phonetic blur as they do not affect the meaning.

1 **1.44** Some other adverbs are commonly rushed in speech. Listen and complete the gaps in the fragments below with the words/phrases in the box.

basically definitely obviously of course particularly

- 1 yeah, _____ computers, you know
- 2 you know, _____ celebrate something
- 3 I was _____ struck
- 4 they've _____ said, well
- 5 I'm _____ pleased because
- 6 It was _____ the best year of my life.
- 7 earlier and _____ he, one of the things he
- 8 um, you know, _____ the focus of Lohri is
- 9 panning out, _____ in terms of
- 10 so what do we need for this? _____ mushrooms
- 11 and _____, people who go to visit
- 12 er, _____ there's, there was the sort of
- 13 because _____ after George
- 14 well, _____, it's terribly important

2 **2.54** You're going to hear each of these words in isolation three times.

Then you'll hear them in a short fragment. They've been written as they sound.

Correct them.

- | | | |
|------------|---------|--------------------------|
| 1 kuz | because | 8 responsbu |
| 2 bout | | 9 excepshny |
| 3 praps | | 10 absoo'i |
| 4 praps | | 11 clecting |
| 5 p'tickly | | 12 tradishny |
| 6 p'tickly | | 13 unde |
| 7 probly | | 14 jeck'n (three words!) |

Another distracting feature of informal speech is a large number of 'throw-away' words. These words do not present any informative value but can obstruct understanding of other parts of the utterance. The 'empty' words are always unstressed, so they add up to the phonetic blur. It is helpful to learn how to detect and ignore them.

3 You will hear four people speaking. What are their favourite 'throw away' words? Write them the name.

- Speaker 1: Frank I mean
- Speaker 2: Debbie _____
- Speaker 3: Kimberly _____
- Speaker 4: Greg _____

4 Underline the 'throw away' words in this text. There are nine more expressions to underline.

We don't like have coffee breaks, I mean we just like get a coffee or tea and sort of like take it back to our desks, you know, but it's kind of dangerous 'cause, I mean, people sometimes like knock the drink over the computer, you know.

5 **2.35** Listen and show where the speaker inserts *you know* using ▲.

- 1 well, yeah, no, it's one of those things like anything else
- 2 it just kind of happens, what I mean, it's not until it's all over
- 3 now we have to have another one, what I mean
- 4 and so you don't really stop
- 5 they wouldn't do that
- 6 but I, so, it, I just got involved
- 7 it was the thing that opened my eyes. It was really
- 8 and artists didn't do that back then. You did covers
- 9 I write the song in 30 minutes. And then sometimes I deliberate over it
- 10 I could tell you why I wrote every single song
- 11 something solid like that
- 12 um, it's better when it comes at the same time
- 13 me, a, a guitar and 40 years of songs that I can draw from
- 14 you want everything to be included. You just do
- 15 can't really imagine having to remember all my friends
- 16 well, I guess, I mean, there seems to be some progress being made on, um, sort of electric cars or just cars that use alternative fuel
- 17 definitely computers, um

6 **2.36** Another common conversational word is *like*. Listen and show where the speaker inserts *like* using ▲.

- 1 it was the best opportunity that I've ever had
- 2 but it seems, sort of, you know, once every five years
- 3 that all happened in sequence
- 4 was it just sort of the eye of the storm
- 5 but it wasn't until, you know, The Beatles
- 6 it was, 'Wow, that's really wonderful'
- 7 um, really good robust decision-making
- 8 a seemingly, you know, simple creature
- 9 um, their nest choice behaviours are very democratic
- 10 so collectively, they're able to, er, vote for a nest
- 11 the sun represents on the one hand the rays of light
- 12 and it's, it's a pagan, pagan ritual
- 13 and they've got, you know, say lorries and buses
- 14 if I see a cyclist now, I'm, 'Oh no'

Decoding fillers and adverbs was less difficult for Sherry, and her reactions were more optimistic.

Lesson 9 Liaison

Intrusion of extra sounds might inhibit understanding as it gives a wrong impression that other words were used.

1) Linking /r/

- Tower of London
- My brother always
- War and peace
- Mother-in-law
- Never again

2) Intrusive /r/

- I saw it
- Law and order
- Draw a circle
- Saw a good film
- Spa in Italy

3) Intrusive /j/

- I agree
- I always
- The end
- Lie on the beach
- High up

4) Intrusive /w/

- Do it
- Go on
- Who is
- Do I have to
- Glue is strong

Sherry was processing information thoroughly, she whispered to herself: ‘Not /aɪ i:t/ but /aɪjt/, not /gəʊ aʊt/ but /gəʊwaʊt/'. The following task showed Sherry the risk liaison presents for comprehension.

1 These sentences have been written as they sound, but they're incorrect. Read them aloud to yourself, then write the correct version.

1 It doesn't get dark till after rate. *It doesn't get dark till after eight.*

2 I studied law rut university.

3 I saw rim coming out of his house.

4 Under-rage drinking's against the law.

5 If your rears are cold, put your hat on.

6 Margaret's got blue wise.

7 It's a quarter to wait.

8 My poor back's starting to wake.

9 He looks pale - is he your right?

10 I can't hear - I've got my fingers in my years!

The issue of catenation, or blurring the word boundaries, closely related to this was addressed in the following tasks.

2 1:75 In these sentences, the part in bold has been misunderstood. Listen and decide what the speaker actually wanted to say. Note that in each bold phrase, there's at least one pronoun which is joined to the word before or after it.

- 1 **abetya** very proud
- 2 **Ana** started to cry
- 3 **telya hawa** feel about 'im
- 4 'cause **anew iwez** excited
- 5 **Ana** did, **agot** very, very emotional
- 6 but **akump** bear to watch it
- 7 **aget** very nervous **forrim**
- 8 **Ana** hadn't realized
- 9 **ani** had the scars **wenee** came back
- 10 **aldoo** it
- 11 **will** never know **kuzwi** broke the boat
- 12 **athing** one or two people were slightly seasick
- 13 because **yether** great-niece
- 14 **yenoe wada** mean
- 15 **shiad** very young friends
- 16 **budakan** still read my
- 17 **yukandoo** a lot of things on the phone
- 18 **anell** come and **meepmi** at the bus stop

I bet you're very proud and I started to cry

3 2:14 You're going to hear ten speech wrongly written fragments, which you'll the them correctly.

- 1 the na natom *than an atom*
- 2 it srit nup
- 3 thin kabout
- 4 eva non
- 5 ka ti tup
- 6 suddenly take so na
- 7 thing a thing kabout
- 8 determin di yiz
- 9 stop tat the scene
- 10 mau than nose

4 The word *rise* is 'hidden' in this sentence: *Her eyes are open*. It is the underlined part. This is clear if we look at the phonemic spelling. The word *rise* is /raɪz/. You can see this underlined in this phonemic spelling of the sentence: /hɒrəɪzərəʊpən/. The words in the box are 'hidden' in the sentences below. Find them and underline them, and write the hidden word after the sentence.

wait rage winter ~~years~~ reach years why rise ride wake

EXAMPLE The boat's useless without the oars. *HOUS*

- 1 Are you into golf?
- 2 He has hair over the ears.
- 3 It's starting to ache.
- 4 I'm not sure I'd agree with you.
- 5 She has a shower each morning.
- 6 It's quarter to eight already.
- 7 Do I owe you anything?
- 8 Her eyes are a strange colour.
- 9 You should know better at your age!

Sherry showed much enthusiasm, but in general, her decoding was less effective than last time. The second task presented an extreme challenge for her. In general, the lesson was very productive, though a little overloaded. In the end, Sherry said her 'brain was tired,' but 'happy,' she added.

Looking back, I think I should have switched Lesson 8 and 9 to allow more time to practice catenation and boost Sherry's motivation by having a relatively easy decoding task by the end of the project.

Lesson 10 Recap

I asked Sherry to bring all her previous home tasks. I prepared a printout called 'How to create an obscure acoustic blur' (Cauldwell: 2013) (see Appendix 2). It helped Sherry summarize everything that had been covered in one table. Before rereading the scripts, I asked Sherry to detect all the features we recently learnt. I believe repetition is effective for teaching listening and pronunciation. Multiple exposures to the patterns make them more recognizable in the future (Field: 2008). To my great satisfaction, Sherry became more fluent in her 'connected' reading.

The content was slightly over planned for a one-hour lesson. Allowing extra time for the points above and linking them back to the project content would have helped Sherry internalize them better.

Part 3. Conclusion

3.1 Outcomes

I rejected the idea of having the final assessment because I did not expect my student to show a radical improvement in her listening after only fifteen hours of coursework. Instead, I was assessing Sherry's improvement through a series of informal observations.

After the last lesson, I asked Sherry to reflect on the work she had done. I assured her that the honest replies could help me further develop my project. Sherry's feedback provided valuable information about her uptake of the lessons; it generally correlated with my vision of the project outcomes.

According to her comments, Sherry highly valued the input she received. She named 'learn the rules', 'know why,' 'difference between natural pronunciation and dictionaries' among what she had learnt. Also, she said she would keep her notes for future use; it made me believe the awareness-raising objective of my work was fully met.

Sherry found listening exercises 'the most interesting'. 'The most difficult' for her was the production part. I noticed that Sherry could read aloud in a 'connected' manner, but when speaking freely, she was mentally preoccupied with lexis and grammar, so she often forgot to 'connect the words'. Sometimes she noticed it and self-corrected it; sometimes, I reminded her. Overall, more productive work is desirable.

Regarding decoding, Sherry used to express much frustration when the project just started. Gradually she was mastering her micro-listening skills. By the end of the project, she could generally do the listening tasks faster than in the beginning. However, her progress was not consistent. While Sherry has gained much confidence with assimilation and elision, vowel reduction still needs more attention. Nevertheless, Sherry assessed her progress in listening 4 out of 5, which was beyond my expectations. All above brings me to the conclusion that the project's objectives and the goal were mainly achieved.

Acknowledging that much more practice is needed for the real progress in pronunciation and listening, Sherry arrived at the end of the project with an optimistic view: 'I will feel so happy I can absorb what my teacher Kate taught.' She was going to accompany her son to his university in Melbourne; in this regard, she wrote, 'I'll try to apply it more when I go overseas'.

3.2 Evaluation

Generally effective, my project has some space for improvement. The movie episodes were quite long given the scale of the project. Chunking them into shorter clips will be helpful.

Regarding the input format, I believe handwriting promotes deeper processing of new information than simple reading from printouts. Also, the handwritten notes stay longer as people generally value them more. However, writing the examples required Sherry considerably long. I am not convinced this time was well worth spending. Next time I will deliver the materials partly in print.

My student's opinion suggests that my project would have benefited from including a deeper insight into English stress, which is essential for understanding the process of vowel reduction. Sherry points out in her reflection that the pronunciation of grammar words was her greatest discovery. Also, she puts 'schwa' in the 'need improvement' box. Thus, I see it reasonable to invest more time teaching how to unstress or 'eat the words' next time.

Had I extended the project's time limit, I would have included another few phonological elements - the glottal stop and dark 'l'. While they rarely affect intelligibility in speaking, they might present a certain difficulty in listening.

In the future, I plan to implement IPA in teaching listening. If written in the phonemic script, the dialogues will serve as a visual representation of the speech, which will enhance the decoding processes. Like alphabetic reading promotes correct spelling, reading in phonetic script promotes 'connected' pronunciation.

Sometime after the project, I found another valuable resource for teaching listening tubequizard.com, which I plan to include in my teaching in the future.

I reduced the original content of the lessons as each element required more attention than expected. Despite the adjustment, I still find the final project quite cognitively heavy. The content could easily make a 6-month program. I see how I can develop this project into a coherent syllabus for the intensive listening course. The course needs to be more practical than the project, with a 30/70 split of input versus output. Alternatively, some components of the project can be integrated into the general English course.

References:

1. BBC Learning English (2017). *Pronunciation Workshops* [video]. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x6wLCnaHsJU&list=PLcetZ6gSk96-ayXj5thbTpbh2vHWpP08o&index=23> [Accessed 20 June 2019]
2. Cauldwell, R. (2013). *Phonology for listening*. Birmingham: Speech in Action
3. Cauldwell, R. (2013). *Jungle Listening: high- and low-tech approaches to teaching the stream of speech* [seminar] Available at: <http://englishagenda.britishcouncil.org/continuing-professional-development/teacher-educator-framework/knowning-subject/jungle-listening-high-and-low-tech-approaches-teaching-stream-speech> [Accessed 13 May 2019]
4. Cauldwell, R. (2002) Grasping the nettle: The importance of perception work in listening R. comprehension, Copyright 2000-2016© Developing Teachers.com; http://www.developingteachers.com/articles_tchtraining/perception1_richard.htm
5. Cauldwell, R. (2003) The two-sides rule in teaching listening and pronunciation; Available at http://www.developingteachers.com/articles_tchtraining/two_sides1_richard.htm;
6. Field, J. (2008) *Listening in language classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
7. Hancock, M. (2013) *Making sense of connected speech*. [online]. Hancock McDonald English language teaching Available at: <http://hancockmcdonald.com/talks/pronunciation-listeners-making-sense-connected-speech> [Accessed 11 Apr 2019]
8. Hancock, M. (2014). *Authentic listening pack*. Surrey: DELTA Publishing
9. Hancock, M. (2003). *English Pronunciation in use*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
10. Hancock, M. (2014). *Pronunciation as a listening skill*. [online] Hancock McDonald English language teaching Available at: <http://hancockmcdonald.com/talks/pronunciation-listening-skill-understanding-connected-speech> [Accessed 11 Apr 2019]
11. Hancock, M. (2012). *Sweden slides* [pdf] Hancock McDonald English language teaching Available at: <http://hancockmcdonald.com/sites/hancockmcdonald.com/files/file-downloads/Hancock%20Sweden%20slides.pdf> [Accessed 20 June 2019]
12. Jenkins, J. (1998). Which pronunciation norms and models for English as an International language? *ELT Journal* Volume 52(2), pp. 119-26
13. Kelly, G. (2018) *How to teach pronunciation*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
14. Redston, C. (2014). *They talk too fast! Helping students with listening* [webinar]. Available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5MyoxMLaHc8&list=PLwFxxcFmB_6ZGD3-pYMuA0MY9jgmBx0EZ&index=12 [Accessed 19 June 2019]
15. Thorn, S. Debunking authentic listening, www.onlineMET.com, *Modern English Teacher* Volume 21 (2), pp. 65-69
16. Thorn, S. (2013) *Real lives, Real listening* London: Harper Collins Publishers
17. Underhill, A. (2004) *The Sounds Foundation*. Oxford: Macmillan Heinemann

Appendix 1. Links to the movie episodes assigned for home practice.

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(1/10\) Movie CLIP - Can I Have Your Autograph? \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(2/10\) Movie CLIP - William Runs Into Anna \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(3/10\) Movie CLIP - A Spontaneous Kiss \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(4/10\) Movie CLIP - Questions & Apologies \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(5/10\) Movie CLIP - Best Friends Already \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(6/10\) Movie CLIP - What Do You Do? \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(7/10\) Movie CLIP - Brownie Contest \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(8/10\) Movie CLIP - Friendly Banter \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(9/10\) Movie CLIP - Just a Girl \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

[\(56\) Notting Hill \(10/10\) Movie CLIP - The Wrong Decision \(1999\) HD - YouTube](#)

Appendix 2. How to create an obscure acoustic blur (Cauldwell: 2013)

	Guidelines	Non-prominent soundshapes	Example speech units
1	Make 'past tense' t and d inaudible in front of both consonants and vowels	realised she > realise she realised it was > realise it was	HE realise she was GONE I realise it was HER
2	Remove final t and d before consonants and vowels	left bank > leff bank left open > leff open against it > again sit kind of > kyne uv	it's ON the leff bank NOW it WAS leff open aGAIN HE'S again sit NOW HE'S kyne of NICE
3	Make the final t of <i>that</i> and <i>at</i> into glottal stops before consonants and vowels	that must > ðæʔ muss at our > æʔ our at about > æʔ about	i'm SURE tha'muss HURT SHE'S a'our house NOW i'll be THERE a'about TEN
4	Remove the initial consonant ð of <i>that</i> , <i>this</i> , <i>the</i> after both consonants and vowels	realise that > realizat and then > annen in the > inner for this > for iss see that > see ut	I realizat i'd LEFT it he CAME annen WENT i SAW them inner GARDen i've PLANS foriss EVENing can YOU see ut it's GOOD
5	Make every diphthong a monophthong based on its first element	realise > rill eyes my time > ma tam boy's a > bore's a able > ebble out of > atta south > saath	I rill eyes it's LOST he SAID ma tam's FINished she SAID the bore's a FOOL he's NOT ebble to DO that HE'S atta LUCK in NORTH and saath LONdon
6	Avoid full closure for the stop consonants p,t,b,d	purse > furss cut it > currit kɔrit a lot of > a lorruv produce > pro-use middle > mill able > ale total > toll	i LEFT my furss at HOME it's BETter to currit OPEN he SPOKE a lorruv SENSE in ORDER to pro-use COFFee NEAR the mill of the PAGE he's NOT ale to COME it's NOT the toll COST
7	Change θ in <i>think</i> to h	think > hink	the ANswer i hink is NO
8	Make final z sound similar to s	eyes > ice does > duss	she ONLY had ice for HIM the WAY it duss THAT

	Guidelines	Non-prominent soundshapes	Example speech units
9	Simplify clusters by removing one or two elements.	first call > furs call first of all > furs of all keeps on > kees on	my VEry furs CALL furs of all HE was LATE he JUST kees on GOing
10	Drop k in <i>extra</i> , <i>expected</i>	extra > estra expected > espected	it's ONE estra COpy DON'T expect him SOON
11	Drop k and t from <i>next</i>	next time > ness time	we'll DO it ness TIME
12	Omit the initial segment of the first word in a speech unit	if you've a > few vuh	few vuh MINute to SPARE
13	Make negative morphemes close to inaudible.	illegal > legal	OTher legal DRUGS
14	Remove weak middle syllables from three syllable words	cont.ra.ry > cont.ry diff.i.cult > diff.cult fin.a.lly > fine.ly	it ISn't contry to THAT it WAS a diffcul TIME and THEN finely THIS one
15	Drop weak syllables from the edges of words	year ago > year go another > noth nʌð	a YEAR go that i WENT WAS there noth QUESTION
16	Take care to mess up <i>have</i> clusters	you have a > yavva you are having > yavving to have a > tavva	i SEE yavva NEW one TELL him yavving a MEAL it's TIME tavva CHAT
17	Don't repeat a segments which are next to each other, and similar	year ahead > year head	PLAN the year head NOW
18	Make two words into one	too early > twirly go over > gover gəʊvə	it's FAR twirly to SAY i'm GOing to gover NOW
19	Make t vowel-like	feel > fee-oo fi:ʊ (sounds close to phew)	DON'T fee-oo so BAD

Appendix 3. Student reflection form

1. Do you find the content of the project useful? Why?

Yes, The project is very useful. I can know why I always can't get most of natives saying. They pronounce different from we have been taught.

2. Which kind of activity during the project you find most practical/interesting/enjoyable?

The table of grammar words and listening ^{exercise} are the most interesting part of the projects. I can realize how ^{big} difference between natural English and what can find from dictionaries.

3. Which was the most difficult for you?

I guessed the pronunciation is the most difficult for me. To pronounce it naturally and fluently.

4. Which aspect of connected speech you find most helpful for better comprehension?

I think to learn some rules and particular forms of connected speech are the most helpful.

5. What was your greatest discovery during the project?

I found the verbs, personal pronouns, prepositions, conjunctions, articles, and Indefinite adjectives are the greatest discovery, because they always pronounce out of your thought.

6. Which aspect of connected speech you have made the greatest progress in?

I believed which is the assimilation.

7. Which aspects you need to further work on?

I think the swah「ə」 sound.

8. What hasn't been covered in the project but you would like to learn more about?

I am not capable to discover.... I only knew I have learned a lot. But still feel I'm beyond too far... I can absorb what my teacher force taught. I'll feel so happy.

9. How would you assess your progress in understanding spontaneous speech on the scale 1 2 3 ④ 5 ?

10. Have you started to apply principles of connected speech to your own speech? Can you feel the difference in your pronunciation before and after the project?

Yes, but I'll try to apply it more once I go overseas. I think my pronunciation will be more natural.

11. Do you find it less scary to listen to the fast native English after the project?

Yes, I do. It's kind of challenge, it is very difficult although.

12. Please share your feedback on the format of the lessons and give some comments about the project in general.

Actually, I really enjoy the lessons very much. Firstly, I learn the rules first, and secondly, I learned more from some examples, Thirdly, I have to find some examples and movie scripts as the homework. Fourthly, The teacher correct and go through with me. It's awesome!

Sherry Tsz